

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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THE ROLE OF ANCESTORS' HERITAGE IN EDUCATING YOUTH IN PATRIOTIC SPIRIT

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the urgent problem of an important aspect of youth education - upbringing in the spirit of patriotism. This article can be used by university students, independent researchers, and a wide audience.

Keywords: Patriotism, youth, high morality, spirituality and enlightenment, work conscientiously relationship, science, national values.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена актуальной проблеме важного аспекта воспитания молодежи – воспитания в духе патриотизма. Эта статья может быть использована студентами вузов, независимыми исследователями и широкой аудиторией.

Ключевые слова: Патриотизм, молодежь, высокая нравственность, духовность и просвещение, добросовестное трудовое отношение, наука, национальные ценности.

Introduction. Our country head Shavkat Mirziyoev January 19, 2021 day spiritual and educational affairs system fundamentally improvement, this is about state and public organizations' cooperation to strengthen issues dedicated conducted at the meeting, "If the society of life body economy if his soul and spirit is spirituality, We are new Uzbekistan set up to do decision did we are two strong to the column we rely The first is the market principles based on a strong economy. The second is the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values based on strong spirituality ", - he said emphasized.

That's why today in Uzbekistan personnel preparation system formation and activity show the main principle in the style of « reader young people Homeland loyalty, high morality, spirituality and enlightenment, work conscientiously to be in the spirit education » separately emphasized. This is it principle based on the national education system and pedagogical-methodical in the fields of fast changes, and intense updates face gave. There are textbook, manual, and program time requirements adjusted step by step to consumption being released. Modern lesson concept from new polished.

From the student's Obedience to the teacher each one the word by heart not required to receive was put Now each school student his own opinion and his protection to do to the right possession, teacher dictator not to science road pointer that he is the leader knows. Given privilege and rights abuse not to be done for

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teacher's deep knowledge and leader-leadership features with armaments it is necessary

Pedagogy point of view in terms of than, subject on the surface national education system and pedagogical-methodical directions within many scientific research, fundamental research done increased. The same problem is only in Uzbekistan it's not perhaps own to the future indifference didn't happen abroad systematically in countries studied and serious research works the world face saw. In our republic and abroad publications scientific and pedagogical books analyze education of the process current directions according to series scientific affairs take going showed. Among them, R.Djuraev, R.Ahmidinov, J.Yoldoshev, EG'oziev, Sh.Kurbanov, E.Seytkhalilov, M.Mirqosimov, U.Inoyatov, O.Musurmonova, M.Saidov, L.Peregudov, Yu. Vasiliev, T.Davidenko, M.Potashnik, V.Simonov, P.Tretyakov, V.Arnautov, V.Monakhov, B.Wulfov, V.Ivanov, V.Bespalko, V.Guzeev, S.Islamgulova, M.Mirkosimova, M. Klarin, I. Podlasiy, N. Saidahmedov, M. Kuronov, B. Tokhliev, N. Komilov, I. Haqqul, Q. Yoldoshev, Q. Husanboeva, B. Ziyomukhamedov, O'. Tolipov, M. Usmonboeva, U. Dolimov and that's it such as scientists education manage its laws state and person the need and interests in satisfaction held place, society development depends on requirements, a perfect person bring up methods research have reached

new Uzbekistan prosperity, future strategy about thought are conducted since the whole republic education in the system big changes done is increasing. Teachers this reforms present reached information communicative and advanced study technologies, modularized and modern education methods using young people spiritual and moral improvement, deep citizenship feeling form, lie ideological from the effects protector ideological immunity harvest to do and teaching efficiency from providing consists of

To this end, young people national the idea in the spirit education in their homeland and Eli with to be proud, to be ready for protection feeling in development literary of education place incomparable. This is its condition and intense information flow because of in our youth abroad countries marriage style aspiration, imitation, nationality away, interstate nuclear not ideological struggle take going continuously literary education system main subject - in students patriotism feeling bring up their roots scientific-pedagogical problem as research reach current that determines.

These tasks solution of doing important from the conditions one literary in education young people spirituality development experiences thoroughness and

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diligent with study, traditional of education today's day for own relevance lost principles give up past, modern, experience himself justified method and to technologies appeal from doing consists of

Uzbek's national education system is also advanced experiencing acceptance to do together a thousand years during formed oriental of methods did not give up. East, in particular, Uzbek education in the system young people education, ethics, patriotism, hard work, humanitarianism such as to adjectives from time immemorial separate attention directed. In this, " Kabusnoma ", " Qutadgu" "Knowledge ", " Hibat -ul Haqaiyiq ", and "Mahbub-ul Qulub " are masterpieces of works relied on.

In our opinion, every how education and education « Education from what starts?" question with started ok. In this teacher personality, opportunities, his to the students and of students to teachers relations such as serious to issues answer is sought.

For example, Alisher Navoi's Turkish language (Uzbek language) wealth demonstration appears from the language pride feeling to the students to mean, to convey it is necessary for Students attention Alisher Navoi speech and the language that's it in the period one sentence using (" Language that's all honor with to the speech service does ») by distinguishing that he gave focus need.

And Ibn Sina 900 years after Trubeskoi sounded vowel and consonants separate, correlative sounds set that he gave about to know in the pupil national pride feeling strengthens. Literary education of the state internal to politics actively affects a social event. In the country education residences success and prosperity symbolize equality to the future successors good leads to actions.

It is known that education **individual**, **rivalry**, and **cooperation** such as three types there is. Individual education using the pedagogue of the pupil to the heart, to the soul right effect is enough Healthy competition using the student's personal and scientific qualities to maturity delivers. In partnership education, the student teaching or from upbringing according to him who studies, is brought up to the situation. In this, each student relentlessly takes himself himself analysis of success and defects conclusion releases.

Human are higher to value what has become education above the three types provided. High value considered student spirituality and to the person to be placed main and the first requirement is patriotism. This requirement satisfies the most efficient and reliable method him literary education through come true release is considered

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Already people to the good inviting, from evil returning is science. She is beautiful morality forms a person's spiritual maturity and delivers " Ethics is this behavior set. Behavior while goodness or of consent certain one in man manifestation to form. Therefore, everyone's behavior of goodness and nobility or vice and pessimism is symbolized. In this respect they are good and for the worse are divided. But these are in a person by itself appear it won't be. Their formation for known conditions, upbringing need. People from birth bad beings are not born. them certain conditions bad does ... Education born from the day starts and of your life, to the end, until continue is enough He is two from the stage - house and school from upbringing organize found "So, young people patriotism in the spirit bring up initially family in the hearth begins, then Kindergarten, a school such as education stages continue will be delivered. Exactly child patriotism in the family high flying calls not, him feeling known spiritual from preparation only recently possible to learn.

Without education in different stages, the knowledge the student lusts to the vortex down from staying, spiritual values abuse from doing protect can't

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